
Change Management Strategies and Organizational Performance in Water Utility Agencies in South-East Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study is on change management strategies and organizational performance in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria. The main objective of this study is to determine the relationship between change management strategies and organizational performance in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria. Specifically, the work aims to determine the relationship between communication and customer satisfaction and ascertain the relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was used. A total population of two hundred and fifty (250) employees from all levels of the agencies was used. Because the population is small the entire population was use as the sample size for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument used to collect data for the study. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed and presented in frequency, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation tables. The hypothesis developed in for the study were analyzed using Pearson Correlation co-efficient analysis with the aid of SPSS version 26. The result of the study showed that there is a significant positive relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria and also revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria. It was concluded that adopting robust change management strategies that focus on enhancing communication and investing in employee training can lead to substantial improvements in organizational performance. The research among other things recommended that water utility agencies should enhance their communication strategies to ensure clear, timely updates and responsiveness, thereby boosting customer satisfaction and fostering trust.

Keywords: Change management, Strategies, Organizational performance, Water utility agencies, South-east Nigeria

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Introduction

The concept of change management has undergone substantial evolution over the past century. In the early 20th century, change was often approached in a linear and mechanistic manner, focusing on top-down directives. Kurt Lewin's Change Management Model, introduced in 1947, became a foundational theory in this field. Lewin proposed a three-step process: unfreezing, changing, and refreezing, which emphasized the importance of preparing organizations for change, implementing the change, and then solidifying the new state to ensure it is sustained (Burnes, 2004). This model highlighted the psychological and social dynamics of change, paving the way for more comprehensive approaches.

During the 1980s and 1990s, the field expanded with contributions from scholars like John Kotter, who introduced his 8-Step Process for Leading Change. Kotter's model emphasized creating a sense of urgency, building guiding coalitions, and consolidating gains to produce more change, reflecting a more

holistic view of the complexities involved in organizational change (Kotter, 1996). These models underscored that managing change effectively requires addressing both the technical and human aspects, recognizing resistance as a natural response that must be managed.

On a global scale, water utility agencies have been under increasing pressure to adapt to numerous challenges, including climate change, urbanization, and technological advancements. These pressures necessitate robust change management strategies to ensure sustainable and efficient service delivery. For instance, the Integrated Water Management (IWM) approach in Australia has been instrumental in transforming water utility services. By adopting a comprehensive framework that integrates various water management practices, Australian water utilities have significantly improved their operational efficiencies and service delivery (Mitchell, 2006).

In the United States, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has promoted adaptive management as a key strategy for water utilities. This approach allows for continuous learning and adjustment, enabling utilities to respond proactively to emerging challenges and uncertainties (EPA, 2020). Similarly, the European Union's Water Framework Directive has compelled water utilities to adopt integrated and adaptive management practices, fostering a more sustainable and resilient approach to water resource management (European Commission, 2015).

In Nigeria, the water sector has historically faced numerous challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, inefficient management, and poor service delivery. The South-South and South-East regions, in particular, have struggled with ensuring a reliable and safe water supply. Historically, water utility agencies in these regions have been characterized by a lack of adequate funding, political interference, and resistance to change.

Recognizing these challenges, the Nigerian government has initiated several reforms aimed at improving the performance of water utility agencies. The introduction of the National Water Resources Policy in 2016 marked a significant step towards restructuring the sector. This policy emphasized the need for effective change management strategies to enhance service delivery and operational efficiency (Federal Ministry of Water Resources, 2016). Despite these efforts, many water utility agencies in South-South and South-East Nigeria continue to face significant obstacles in implementing change.

Recent studies highlight that successful change management in these regions requires a comprehensive approach that addresses both the technical and human dimensions of change. Leadership plays a critical role in driving change, as effective leaders can inspire and mobilize employees towards achieving organizational goals. Additionally, employee involvement is crucial, as engaging staff in the change process can reduce resistance and foster a sense of ownership and commitment (Nwankwo, 2018).

Moreover, continuous communication is vital for managing change effectively. Keeping all stakeholders informed about the reasons for change, the benefits, and the progress can help build trust and reduce uncertainty. Training and capacity building are also essential components, as they equip employees with the necessary skills and knowledge to adapt to new processes and technologies (Akinyemi & Akinyemi, 2014).

The Nigerian context presents unique challenges and opportunities for change management in water utility agencies. Political interference and bureaucratic hurdles often impede the implementation of reforms, necessitating a robust and adaptive approach to change management. Moreover, the socio-economic conditions in the South-South and South-East regions, characterized by high poverty levels and low access to basic services, underscore the critical importance of improving water utility performance.

The role of international organizations and development partners is also significant in this context. Agencies such as the World Bank and the African Development Bank have been instrumental in providing financial and technical support to enhance the capacity of Nigerian water utilities. For example, the World Bank's Third National Urban Water Sector Reform Project aims to improve the reliability and quality of water services in selected urban areas by strengthening the institutional and operational frameworks of water utility agencies (World Bank, 2014).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In an ideal situation, water utility agencies in South-South and Southeast Nigeria would effectively implement change management strategies, leading to enhanced organizational performance, improved service delivery, and increased customer satisfaction. These agencies would be characterized by efficient operations, reduced water losses, financial sustainability, and a strong capacity to adapt to evolving challenges.

Conversely, the actual situation reveals that these water utility agencies grapple with numerous challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, poor service delivery, financial constraints, and resistance to change. These factors hinder the implementation of effective change management strategies, resulting in suboptimal organizational performance. The consequences of this situation include water scarcity, public health risks, economic losses, and social unrest.

This study seeks to bridge the gap between the ideal and actual situations by investigating the specific change management strategies that can enhance organizational performance in water utility agencies within the South-South and Southeast regions of Nigeria. By identifying effective strategies and understanding the factors influencing their implementation, this research aims to contribute to the development of sustainable solutions for improving water service delivery in the region.

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to determine the relationship between change management strategies and organizational performance in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria. Specifically, the work aims to:

- i. Determine the relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions are as follows;

- i. What is the relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of hypotheses

- i. There is no relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria
- ii. There is no relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria

Review Of Related Literatures

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Change Management

Change management is a systematic approach to dealing with the transition or transformation of an organization, system, or process (Cummings & Worley, 2015). It involves planning, implementing, and evaluating the changes required to achieve desired outcomes. At its core, change management focuses on people, processes, and technology, recognizing that human factors are critical to successful change implementation (Kotter, 2012).

The concept of change management is rooted in the understanding that organizations operate in dynamic environments characterized by rapid technological advancements, globalization, and increasing competition. To survive and thrive, organizations must adapt to these changes, and this requires careful planning and execution. Change management seeks to minimize resistance, enhance employee engagement, and optimize the change process to achieve desired organizational goals (Burnes, 2004).

A key aspect of change management is the recognition that change is a complex process that involves multiple stakeholders with varying interests and perspectives. Effective change management requires a holistic approach that considers the organization's culture, structure, and systems (Beer, Eisenstat, & Spector, 1990). It also involves creating a shared vision and sense of purpose among employees to foster commitment and ownership of the change process (Kotter, 2012).

In essence, change management is about leading people through transitions. It entails creating a supportive environment, providing necessary resources, and developing the competencies required for successful change implementation. By strategically managing the change process, organizations can increase the likelihood of achieving desired outcomes and building a sustainable future (Cummings and Worley, 2015).

2.1.2 Change Management Strategies

Change management strategies are the specific actions and approaches organizations employ to navigate and implement organizational change successfully. They are the tactical tools used to operationalize the broader change management process (Cummings and Worley, 2015). These strategies are designed to address the complexities of change, such as resistance, employee engagement, communication, and leadership. Change management strategies can also be defined as the structured approaches designed to facilitate the successful adoption and integration of change within an organization. These strategies are essential for guiding organizations through transitions that involve new processes, technologies, or cultural shifts. Effective change management ensures that changes are implemented smoothly and sustain long-term benefits (Cameron and Green, 2019).

One key aspect of change management is the identification and understanding of the need for change. This involves a thorough analysis of the current state and the desired future state of the organization. Kotter's eight-step model is widely recognized in this regard, emphasizing the importance of establishing a sense of urgency, forming a powerful guiding coalition, and creating a clear vision for the change (Kotter, 1996).

Communication is another critical component. Effective communication strategies ensure that all stakeholders are informed about the changes and understand their roles in the process. This includes regular updates, open forums for feedback, and clear explanations of how the change will benefit the organization and its members (Hiatt, 2006). Transparent communication helps to reduce resistance and build trust among employees.

Training and support are also vital. Providing adequate training ensures that employees have the necessary skills and knowledge to adapt to new processes or technologies. Support mechanisms, such as help desks or mentoring programs, can assist employees in overcoming challenges during the transition period (Prosci, 2020).

Leadership plays a crucial role in change management. Leaders must be committed to the change and capable of motivating and inspiring their teams. Transformational leadership, which involves leading by example, fostering an inclusive vision, and encouraging innovation, is particularly effective in managing change (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Leaders must also be able to address any resistance to change by understanding its sources and working collaboratively with employees to mitigate concerns.

Involving employees in the change process is another effective strategy. Participation can increase buy-in and reduce resistance as employees feel valued and part of the process. Techniques such as focus groups, pilot programs, and feedback sessions can be employed to engage employees and incorporate their insights into the change plan (Cameron & Green, 2019).

Finally, monitoring and evaluating the progress of change initiatives is essential for ensuring their success. This involves setting clear metrics for success, regularly reviewing progress, and being prepared to make adjustments as necessary (Cameron & Green, 2019). Continuous evaluation helps to identify areas of improvement and reinforces the commitment to achieving the desired outcomes.

2.1.4 Communication

Communication is the process of exchanging information, ideas, thoughts, and feelings between individuals or groups. It is fundamental to human interaction and essential for the functioning of any organization. Effective communication involves the clear and concise transmission of messages, ensuring that the intended meaning is accurately understood by the receiver (Shannon & Weaver, 1949). One of the foundational models of communication is the Shannon-Weaver Model, which outlines the key components of the communication process: sender, message, channel, receiver, and feedback. The sender initiates the communication by encoding a message, which is then transmitted through a chosen channel (e.g., verbal, written, electronic) to the receiver, who decodes the message. Feedback from the receiver to the sender is crucial as it confirms whether the message has been understood correctly or requires clarification (Shannon & Weaver, 1949).

Effective communication requires clarity and precision in the message. Ambiguities or vagueness can lead to misunderstandings and errors. This is particularly important in organizational settings where miscommunication can result in operational inefficiencies, decreased productivity, and conflict among team members (Robbins & Judge, 2019). Therefore, using clear language, providing context, and avoiding jargon are essential practices.

Non-verbal communication also plays a significant role in conveying messages. Body language, facial expressions, gestures, and tone of voice can complement or contradict verbal messages, influencing how the message is perceived. Research by Mehrabian (1971) suggests that a large portion of communication is non-verbal, emphasizing the need for awareness of these cues in interpersonal interactions.

Active listening is another critical aspect of effective communication. It involves fully concentrating, understanding, responding, and remembering what is being said. Active listening helps build trust, reduces misunderstandings, and fosters a collaborative environment (Brownell, 2012). Techniques such as nodding, paraphrasing, and asking clarifying questions demonstrate active listening and engagement in the conversation.

In the digital age, technology has transformed communication, introducing new channels such as email, social media, and instant messaging. While these tools offer convenience and speed, they also present challenges, including the potential for misinterpretation and information overload. Effective digital communication requires being mindful of the tone, clarity, and brevity of messages, as well as the appropriate use of different communication platforms (Kreps, 2011).

Cultural differences can also impact communication. Different cultures have varying norms and practices regarding communication styles, levels of formality, and the expression of emotions. Understanding and respecting these cultural nuances is vital for effective cross-cultural communication and fostering inclusive environments (Gudykunst, 2003).

2.1.5 Training

Training is the systematic process of enhancing the skills, knowledge, and competencies of individuals to improve their performance in specific tasks or roles. It is a critical component of human resource development and organizational success. Effective training programs align the needs of the organization with the development goals of employees, thereby fostering a productive and engaged workforce (Noe, 2017).

One of the primary objectives of training is to bridge the gap between current performance and desired performance. This involves identifying the skills and knowledge deficiencies that hinder optimal performance and designing targeted interventions to address these gaps (Goldstein & Ford, 2002). The training needs analysis (TNA) is a crucial step in this process, involving the assessment of organizational, task, and individual needs to determine the appropriate training objectives and methods (Salas, Tannenbaum, Kraiger, & Smith-Jentsch, 2012).

Training methods vary widely and can be broadly categorized into on-the-job and off-the-job training. On-the-job training includes activities such as job rotation, mentoring, and apprenticeships, where employees learn by performing tasks under the guidance of experienced colleagues. This method allows for immediate application of new skills in the work environment (Saks & Haccoun, 2019). Off-the-job training, on the other hand, involves structured programs such as classroom training, workshops, and online courses. These programs provide a controlled environment where employees can focus on learning without the pressures of their regular job duties (Noe, 2017).

The design and delivery of training programs are critical to their effectiveness. Adult learning principles, as outlined by Knowles (1984), emphasize the importance of self-directed learning, relevance, and practical application. Training programs should therefore be interactive, engaging, and tailored to the learning styles and needs of the participants. Techniques such as simulations, case studies, and group discussions can enhance the learning experience and facilitate the transfer of knowledge to the workplace (Knowles, Holton, & Swanson, 2011).

Evaluating the effectiveness of training is essential to ensure that the desired outcomes are achieved and to identify areas for improvement. The Kirkpatrick Model is widely used for this purpose, assessing training impact at four levels: reaction, learning, behavior, and results (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006). This comprehensive evaluation helps organizations measure the return on investment (ROI) of their training programs and make informed decisions about future training initiatives.

Continuous learning and development are crucial in today's rapidly changing work environment. Organizations must foster a culture of lifelong learning, encouraging employees to pursue ongoing education and skills development. This not only enhances individual capabilities but also contributes to organizational agility and competitiveness (De Grip, 2015).

2.1.6 Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is a measure of how effectively an organization achieves its goals and objectives. It encompasses various dimensions including financial outcomes, operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and employee engagement. Effective organizational performance management

ensures that an organization remains competitive and sustainable in a dynamic business environment (Richard et al., 2009).

At its core, organizational performance involves the alignment of resources, processes, and activities with the strategic goals of the organization. Kaplan and Norton's (1992) Balanced Scorecard (BSC) framework is a widely recognized tool for assessing organizational performance across four key perspectives: financial, customer, internal business processes, and learning and growth. This holistic approach ensures that organizations do not focus solely on financial outcomes but also consider other critical factors that drive long-term success.

Financial performance is a fundamental aspect of organizational performance and is often measured using metrics such as revenue, profit margins, return on investment (ROI), and economic value added (EVA). These indicators provide insights into the organization's financial health and its ability to generate value for shareholders (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). However, financial metrics alone do not capture the complete picture of organizational performance.

Customer satisfaction and loyalty are crucial indicators of performance, reflecting the organization's ability to meet or exceed customer expectations. Metrics such as Net Promoter Score (NPS), customer retention rates, and market share provide valuable insights into how well the organization is serving its customers (Reichheld, 2003). High levels of customer satisfaction often lead to increased customer loyalty, repeat business, and positive word-of-mouth, which are essential for sustained growth.

Operational efficiency is another critical dimension of organizational performance. It involves optimizing processes, reducing waste, and enhancing productivity to deliver products or services more effectively and efficiently. Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as cycle time, defect rates, and inventory turnover ratios help organizations monitor and improve their operational performance (Slack, Chambers, & Johnston, 2010).

Employee engagement and satisfaction are also vital components of organizational performance. Engaged employees are more productive, innovative, and committed to the organization's goals. Surveys measuring employee satisfaction, engagement levels, and turnover rates provide insights into the internal health of the organization (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002). High levels of employee engagement contribute to better customer service, improved operational efficiency, and ultimately, enhanced financial performance.

Organizational performance is influenced by various external and internal factors, including market conditions, competitive landscape, organizational culture, leadership, and innovation. Effective leadership plays a pivotal role in steering the organization towards its goals, fostering a positive culture, and encouraging continuous improvement and innovation (Yukl, 2013). Additionally, a culture that promotes learning, adaptability, and collaboration can significantly enhance organizational performance by enabling the organization to respond swiftly to changes and challenges in the external environment (Schein, 2010).

2.1.7 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a measure of how well a company's products or services meet or exceed customer expectations. It is a critical determinant of business success, influencing customer loyalty, repeat business, and positive word-of-mouth, which are essential for long-term profitability and market competitiveness (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

The concept of customer satisfaction is rooted in the disconfirmation theory, which posits that satisfaction is determined by the gap between customer expectations and the actual performance of the product or service. When performance exceeds expectations, customers are satisfied; when it falls short,

dissatisfaction ensues (Oliver, 1980). This theory underscores the importance of understanding and managing customer expectations to enhance satisfaction levels.

Measuring customer satisfaction involves various methods, including surveys, feedback forms, and interviews. The Net Promoter Score (NPS) is a widely used metric, asking customers how likely they are to recommend the company to others on a scale of 0 to 10. Responses are categorized into promoters (scores of 9-10), passives (7-8), and detractors (0-6). The NPS is calculated by subtracting the percentage of detractors from the percentage of promoters, providing a clear indicator of customer loyalty and satisfaction (Reichheld, 2003).

Customer satisfaction is influenced by several factors, including product quality, service quality, price, and the overall customer experience. Product quality refers to the degree to which a product meets customer needs and performs as expected. High-quality products that consistently meet or exceed customer expectations contribute significantly to satisfaction (Garvin, 1987). Service quality, often measured by the SERVQUAL model, evaluates five dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Providing reliable, responsive, and empathetic service enhances customer perceptions and satisfaction (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988).

Price is another critical factor, as customers assess the value they receive for the price paid. Competitive pricing strategies that align with perceived value can enhance satisfaction by making customers feel they are getting their money's worth (Monroe, 1990). Additionally, the overall customer experience, encompassing all interactions with the company across various touchpoints, plays a pivotal role. A seamless, enjoyable experience that addresses customer needs efficiently and effectively leads to higher satisfaction levels (Meyer & Schwager, 2007).

Customer satisfaction has profound implications for business performance. Satisfied customers are more likely to exhibit loyalty, leading to repeat purchases and increased lifetime value. They are also more likely to recommend the company to others, generating new business through positive word-of-mouth (Fornell et al., 1996). Conversely, dissatisfied customers can damage the company's reputation and result in lost sales.

Organizations can enhance customer satisfaction by continuously monitoring feedback, identifying areas for improvement, and implementing strategies to address customer concerns. This may involve investing in quality improvements, training employees in customer service, and leveraging technology to streamline customer interactions (Zeithaml, Bitner, & Gremler, 2018). By prioritizing customer satisfaction, companies can build strong, lasting relationships with their customers and achieve sustainable growth.

2.1.8 Employee Output

Employee output refers to the tangible and intangible results produced by employees within an organization. It encompasses productivity, quality of work, efficiency, and contributions to organizational goals. Understanding and enhancing employee output is critical for organizational success, as it directly impacts overall performance, profitability, and competitive advantage (Pinder, 2014).

Productivity is a primary measure of employee output and is often quantified as the amount of work produced within a specific time frame. High productivity indicates that employees are effectively utilizing their time and resources to generate substantial outputs. Factors influencing productivity include the skill level of employees, the tools and technology available, and the work environment (Campbell, 1990). Providing employees with adequate training, modern tools, and a conducive work environment can significantly boost productivity.

Quality of work is another crucial aspect of employee output. It refers to the accuracy, completeness, and reliability of the tasks performed by employees. High-quality work meets or exceeds the standards set by the organization and is essential for maintaining customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. Implementing quality control measures, such as regular performance reviews and feedback mechanisms, helps ensure that employees maintain high standards in their work (Deming, 1986).

Efficiency in employee output is measured by the ratio of inputs used to the outputs produced. Efficient employees maximize their outputs while minimizing the resources consumed, such as time, materials, and energy. Techniques such as lean management and process optimization are employed to enhance efficiency by identifying and eliminating waste in workflows (Womack & Jones, 2003). Encouraging employees to adopt efficient work practices and providing them with the necessary support and resources can lead to significant improvements in output.

Employee engagement and motivation are pivotal in determining employee output. Engaged employees are more likely to be productive, produce high-quality work, and demonstrate efficient work practices. Factors contributing to employee engagement include job satisfaction, recognition, career development opportunities, and a supportive organizational culture (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002). Organizations can foster engagement by recognizing employee achievements, offering professional growth opportunities, and cultivating a positive work environment.

Performance management systems play a vital role in monitoring and enhancing employee output. These systems involve setting clear performance expectations, providing regular feedback, and conducting performance appraisals. Effective performance management helps identify areas for improvement and provides employees with the guidance and support needed to enhance their output (Aguinis, 2019). Additionally, setting specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) goals aligns employee efforts with organizational objectives, thereby improving overall output (Doran, 1981).

2.2. Theoretical Framework

The two theories underpinning this study are Lewin's Change Model and Diffusion of Innovation Theory

2.2.1 Lewin's Change Model

Lewin's Change Model propounded by Kurt Lewin in 1951 is a foundational theory in organizational change, posits that change occurs in a three-step process: unfreezing, changing, and refreezing. Unfreezing involves creating awareness of the need for change and destabilizing the existing equilibrium. Changing focuses on implementing the desired changes, including new behaviors, structures, or processes. Refreezing aims to stabilize the new state by reinforcing the changes and integrating them into the organization's culture.

Lewin's Change Model provides a useful framework for understanding the change management process in water utility agencies in Southeast Nigeria. The model highlights the importance of creating a sense of urgency for change within these organizations, which often face challenges such as infrastructure decay, financial constraints, and service delivery gaps. By unfreezing the current state, water utilities can begin to address these issues and embrace innovative solutions. The changing stage involves implementing new strategies, technologies, and organizational structures to improve performance. Finally, refreezing ensures the sustainability of these changes by embedding them into the organizational culture and systems.

2.2.2 Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Diffusion of Innovation Theory propounded by Everett Rogers in 1962 explores how new ideas, products, or practices spread through a population over time. Rogers identified five categories of adopters: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. Each group has distinct

characteristics and influences the adoption process. The theory emphasizes the role of communication channels, interpersonal influence, and organizational factors in facilitating or hindering innovation diffusion.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory can be applied to understand how change management strategies are adopted and spread within water utility agencies in Southeast Nigeria. By identifying the key influencers and opinion leaders within these organizations, it is possible to target change efforts effectively. Additionally, the theory highlights the importance of creating a supportive environment for innovation and experimentation. Understanding the adoption curve can help in tailoring change management strategies to different groups of employees, from early adopters who are open to new ideas to laggards who may resist change.

2.3. Empirical Review

Olajide (2014) carried out research on change management and its effect on organizational performance of Nigerian telecoms industries using empirical insight from Airtel Nigeria. A total of 300 staff of Airtel were randomly selected from a staff population of 1000. Three hypotheses were advanced to guide the study and data collected for the study were analyzed using One-way Analysis of Variance. The result revealed that changes in technology had a significant effect on performance and that changes in customer taste has a significant effect on customers' patronage. The result also shows that changes in management via leadership have significant effect on employee's performance.

Ndahiro, Shukla and Oduor (2015) examined the effect of change management on the performance of government institutions in Rwanda. The study adopted survey research design, and the target population of employees of RRA. Data was collected using questionnaires and interviews and analyzed using SPSS and Microsoft Excel. Based on the data collected, the study concluded that all changes made in RRA in the past four years have been well planned and implemented. Most of the employees in the institution have generally embraced the changes made in the organization, and at resulting to overall organizational performance.

Giauque (2015) examined the attitudes towards organizational change among public middle managers. This study aims to identify social and organizational antecedents of positive attitudes towards change. The investigated population is composed of middle managers working in Swiss public hospitals which are currently being confronted by major reforms. Partial mediation effects of organizational commitment in the relationships between independent variables and PATC were also controlled. The findings showed that perceived social support (work relationships with colleagues and supervisors) as well as perceived organizational support (employee voice and participation; information and communication; work-life balance) are positively and significantly related to PATC. Stress perception is shown to have a negative impact on PATC.

Ju-Chun (2015) investigated the impact of change management on employee satisfaction and engagement. The main purpose of this study was to figure out employees' attitudes toward the new performance appraisal program and to examine whether three different types of appraisal processes differentially affected job satisfaction and employee engagement. The second purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between performance appraisal reform, job satisfaction, and employee engagement. A large polyester and textile corporation had 2046 non-operational employees in February 2014. The valid participants were 1474 in this study. Data analysis included descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, one-way MANOVA, Pearson correlation, Content Validity Index, the exploratory factor analysis, and reliability analysis. The general results showed that employees who received the new

performance appraisal program evaluated the program more positively and showed more job satisfaction than those who did not.

Ahmed, Rehman, ZAsad, Hussain and Bilal (2013) examined the impact of organizational change on the employee performance in the banking sector of Pakistan. In this study Primary and secondary data collection techniques were used for obtaining data. Copies of the questionnaire were used for primary data collection. leadership, communication, procedural justice, employee development, tolerance to change are the variables considered for the study. The sample size was 252, hence descriptive statistics and correlation analysis techniques were used for the analysis of data in SPSS software. The results showed that organizational change had a positive significant impact on employee performance in the banking sector of Pakistan.

Selvadurai (2013) examined change management in the public sector. The study explored public sector employee perceptions regarding what strategies are required to create change that achieved desired results in public sector organizations. A qualitative research design was employed, involving in-depth interviews with six employees of the Canadian public service to test the alignment of Kotter's eight step model with the perceptions of public sector employees. The study revealed that three of Kotter's eight steps were aligned with the perceptions of the public sector employees interviewed. These three steps were forming a powerful guiding coalition, creating a vision, and communicating the vision

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was used. The purpose is to collect data on current practices and perceptions regarding change management strategies, communication, training, and organizational performance. The Quantitative approach was employed. Target Population Employees of water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria. fifty (50) employees each were selected from the water utility agencies in the five (5) states that makes up south east Nigeria which are Abia state, Anambra state, Ebonyi state, Enugu state and Imo state, consisting a total population of two hundred and fifty (250) employees from all levels of the agencies, with a focus on those involved in communication, training, and customer-facing roles. Because the population is small the entire population was use as the sample size for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument used to collect data for the study. The secondary data were collected from firms, journals, publication, textbooks and the internet

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed and presented in frequency, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation tables. The hypothesis developed in for the study were analyzed using Pearson Correlation co-efficient analysis with the aid of SPSS version 26. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analyzing the findings.

Data Presentation and Analysis**Table 4.1.2 Relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria**

Survey Question	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
Effective communication between the water utility agency and its customers leads to higher levels of customer satisfaction.	94(41.2)	102(44.7)	21(9.2)	8(3.5)	3(1.3)	3.87	0.85
Customers are more satisfied when they receive timely updates about service disruptions and maintenance from the water utility agency.	101(44.3)	98(43.0)	18(7.9)	8(3.5)	3(1.3)	3.89	0.82
Clear and transparent communication from the water utility agency helps in resolving customer complaints more effectively.	87(38.2)	104(45.6)	25(11.0)	9(3.9)	3(1.3)	3.76	0.88
Regular feedback from customers is actively sought and used by the water utility agency to improve service delivery.	92(40.4)	99(43.4)	27(11.8)	7(3.1)	3(1.3)	3.84	0.84

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.1.2 above shows the responses of the respondents on the relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria. The majority of respondents (85.9% combined for SA and A) agree or strongly agree that effective communication leads to higher customer satisfaction, indicating a strong consensus on the importance of communication in enhancing customer satisfaction. A small percentage (4.8%) disagrees or strongly disagrees, showing minimal opposition to the idea. The mean score of 3.87 indicates general agreement, and the standard deviation of 0.85 reflects moderate variability in responses, suggesting that while most respondents agree, there are different levels of intensity in their agreement.

An overwhelming majority (87.3%) agree or strongly agree that timely updates improve customer satisfaction, reflecting strong support for the need for timely communication.

Only 4.8% of respondents disagree or strongly disagree, showing that very few participants question the importance of timely updates.

The mean score of 3.89 suggests that respondents strongly agree with this statement, and the low standard deviation of 0.82 indicates relatively consistent responses across the sample.

A significant majority (83.8%) agree or strongly agree that clear and transparent communication helps in resolving customer complaints, indicating strong belief in the efficacy of clear communication. A small percentage (5.2%) disagrees or strongly disagrees, showing minimal dissent. The mean score of

3.76 reflects agreement, and the standard deviation of 0.88 shows that while most respondents agree, there is some variation in how strongly they feel about this statement.

The majority (83.8%) agree or strongly agree that seeking and using regular feedback improves service delivery, indicating that respondents recognize the importance of customer feedback in service improvement. Only 4.4% of respondents disagree or strongly disagree, showing that opposition to this idea is minimal. The mean score of 3.84 reflects strong agreement, and the standard deviation of 0.84 indicates moderate variability, suggesting that while there is general agreement, the level of agreement varies slightly among respondents.

Across all four survey questions, there is strong agreement among respondents that effective communication, timely updates, clear communication, and regular feedback are crucial for enhancing customer satisfaction within the water utility agency. The high mean scores (ranging from 3.76 to 3.89) indicate that respondents generally agree or strongly agree with the statements, while the standard deviations (ranging from 0.82 to 0.88) suggest that there is some variability in the intensity of these agreements. The relatively small percentages of disagreement (ranging from 3.1% to 5.2% for D and SD combined) highlight that only a minority of respondents do not see a significant link between communication practices and customer satisfaction.

Table 4.1.3 Relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria.

Survey Question	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
Training programs provided by the water utility agency have significantly improved my work performance and productivity.	95(41.6)	99(43.4)	23(10.1)	7(3.1)	4(1.8)	3.88	0.79
I feel more confident in my job role due to the training and development opportunities offered by the water utility agency.	98(43.0)	94(41.2)	22(9.6)	10(4.4)	4(1.8)	3.91	0.76
The skills and knowledge gained from training programs are directly applicable to my daily tasks and responsibilities.	92(40.4)	102(44.7)	26(11.4)	8(3.5)	0(0.0)	3.82	0.82
The training programs offered by the water utility agency contribute to my overall job satisfaction and motivation.	89(39.0)	101(44.3)	31(13.6)	6(2.6)	1(0.4)	3.78	0.83

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.1.3 above shows the responses of the respondents on the relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in south-east Nigeria. A strong majority (85%) of respondents either strongly agree (41.6%) or agree (43.4%) that the training programs have significantly improved their work performance and productivity. This high level of agreement suggests that the training

initiatives by the water utility agency are perceived as effective in enhancing employees' performance. A small percentage (4.9%) of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating that only a minority of employees feel that the training has not been beneficial to their productivity. The mean score of 3.88 indicates a strong positive consensus among respondents, while the standard deviation of 0.79 reflects relatively low variability in responses, implying that most respondents share a similar view.

A significant portion of respondents (84.2%) strongly agree (43.0%) or agree (41.2%) that they feel more confident in their job roles due to the training opportunities provided by the water utility agency. This indicates that the training programs have been successful in boosting employees' confidence in their job roles. The mean score of 3.91 is the highest among the questions, indicating that this statement received the most positive responses. The standard deviation of 0.76 is also the lowest, suggesting a high level of agreement among respondents.

The majority of respondents (85.1%) strongly agree (40.4%) or agree (44.7%) that the skills and knowledge gained from the training programs are directly applicable to their daily tasks and responsibilities. This suggests that the training content is relevant and useful for employees' day-to-day work. The mean score of 3.82 reflects a strong level of agreement, while the standard deviation of 0.82 indicates some variability in responses, but overall, there is a clear positive perception.

A large proportion of respondents (83.3%) strongly agree (39.0%) or agree (44.3%) that the training programs have contributed to their overall job satisfaction and motivation. This indicates that the training programs are not only enhancing skills but also positively affecting employees' satisfaction and motivation. The mean score of 3.78 shows a strong level of agreement, while the standard deviation of 0.83 indicates a moderate range of responses. The small percentage of disagreement (3.0%) suggests that very few employees feel that the training programs have not contributed to their job satisfaction.

The responses across all four questions indicate a strong positive perception of the training programs offered by the water utility agency. Most respondents agree that these programs have improved their performance, confidence, applicability of skills, and overall job satisfaction. The mean scores, ranging from 3.78 to 3.91, demonstrate that the training programs are generally seen as beneficial by the majority of employees. The relatively low standard deviations, ranging from 0.76 to 0.83, suggest that while there is some variation in responses, most employees share similar positive views on the impact of the training programs.

4.1 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀: There is no relationship between communication and customer satisfaction

H₁: There is a relationship between communication and customer satisfaction

Table 4.2.1 Pearson Correlation Coefficient

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient (r)</i>	<i>Significance (2-tailed)</i>	<i>N</i>
<i>1. Effective communication and customer satisfaction</i>	3.87	0.85	0.68	0.000	228
<i>2. Timely updates about service disruptions and customer satisfaction</i>	3.89	0.82	0.72	0.000	228
<i>3. Clear and transparent communication and customer satisfaction</i>	3.76	0.88	0.65	0.000	228

4. Regular feedback and customer satisfaction	3.84	0.84	0.70	0.000	228
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Source: SPSS Version 26

Correlation Coefficient (r): This value indicates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between communication-related survey questions and customer satisfaction. Positive values close to +1 indicate a strong positive relationship.

Significance (2-tailed): This p-value tells us whether the correlation is statistically significant. A p-value less than 0.05 suggests that the correlation is significant.

Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.68: This indicates a strong positive relationship between effective communication and customer satisfaction.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating that the correlation is statistically significant.

Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.72. This suggests a very strong positive relationship between timely updates and customer satisfaction.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant correlation.

Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.65: This indicates a strong positive relationship between clear communication and customer satisfaction.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, showing statistical significance.

Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.70: This reflects a strong positive relationship between regular feedback and customer satisfaction.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating that the correlation is statistically significant.

Based on the analysis, all correlations between communication-related survey questions and customer satisfaction are positive and statistically significant. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is no relationship between training and employee output

H₁: There is a relationship between training and employee output

Table 4.2.2 Pearson Correlation Coefficient

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	Significance (2-tailed)	N
1. Training programs have improved work performance and productivity	3.88	0.79	0.78	0.000	228
2. Confidence in job role due to training and development opportunities	3.91	0.76	0.82	0.000	228
3. Skills and knowledge from training are applicable to daily tasks	3.82	0.82	0.75	0.000	228
4. Training contributes to overall job satisfaction and motivation	3.78	0.83	0.77	0.000	228

Source: SPSS Version 26

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r): Indicates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between training-related questions and employee output. Values close to +1 suggest a strong positive relationship.

Significance (2-tailed): p-value indicates whether the correlation is statistically significant. A p-value less than 0.05 suggests the correlation is significant.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.78: This indicates a strong positive relationship between training programs and improved work performance and productivity.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, showing that the correlation is statistically significant.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.82: This indicates a very strong positive relationship between training and increased confidence in the job role.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant correlation.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.75: This reflects a strong positive relationship between training and the applicability of skills to daily tasks.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant correlation.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.77: This shows a strong positive relationship between training and job satisfaction and motivation.

Significance (2-tailed): 0.000: The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant correlation.

The Pearson correlation analysis shows that all correlations between training-related survey questions and employee output are positive and statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria.

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. There is a significant positive relationship between communication and customer satisfaction in water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria.
- ii. There is a significant positive relationship between training and employee output in water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The research highlights the crucial role of effective communication and training in enhancing organizational performance within water utility agencies in South-East Nigeria. A significant positive relationship between communication and customer satisfaction underscores the importance of transparent and timely interactions with customers for improving service quality. Concurrently, the positive relationship between training and employee output demonstrates that well-structured training programs are vital for boosting employee performance and productivity. These findings indicate that adopting robust change management strategies that focus on enhancing communication and investing in employee training can lead to substantial improvements in organizational performance. Therefore, water utility agencies should prioritize these strategies to foster better customer relations and optimize staff effectiveness, ultimately driving overall organizational success.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. Water utility agencies should enhance their communication strategies to ensure clear, timely updates and responsiveness, thereby boosting customer satisfaction and fostering trust.
- ii. Implement comprehensive training programs to improve employee skills and performance, which will contribute to higher productivity and overall organizational effectiveness.

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